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FUTURE OF M-COMMERCE SERVICES IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *Use of mobile phone has increased so much that it is not just a device to make calls, but an important medium to fulfill all the financial needs for friends and family. Now, mobile phone technology has made another leapfrog to pave its way for a new trend called mobile commerce where the financial transactions are made using mobile devices. This paper gives the overview of future of m-commerce services in India and discusses the future growth segment in India's m-commerce. Also find various factors that would essential growth of Indian m-commerce services. In this paper we will found m-commerce exponential growth of m-commerce services in coming years in emerging market of India.*

Design/ Methodology/ Approach: *The Present paper is qualitative and based on secondary data collected from various sources like books newspaper management journal and internet.*

Findings : *Mobile commerce is going to play a major role in mpayment conducting business in future. Future of m-commerce services is very difficult to predict. With heated competition in markets, different mpayment strategies, and more customer awareness give a boost to mobile commerce services growth.*

Limitation : *Present research paper is qualitative in nature and based on secondary data: research could be more authenticated if it would have been based of primary data.*

Practical application : *This paper can inspire the consumer, retailer and experts of their field bringing certain change in mpayment services for better future.*

Originality/ values : *This paper includes practical mpayment services in India and future upcoming trends of mpayment services. This will promote interesting contributions in M-commerce research.*

Key words: *M-commerce, mPayment, Mobile device, Banking & Financial Services*

1. INTRODUCTION:

What is Mobile-payment?

According to data pro research Gartner Mobile payment is any payment transaction involving the purchase of goods or services that is completed with wireless device, such as a cellular phone, personal computer (wireless), or personal digital assistant. Mobile payment is a new emerging way of paying by using a mobile terminal to initiate transaction over a mobile network.

Mobile payment is exciting because it extends the reach of electronic-payment facilities beyond the limitation of the PC or TV to the hundreds of millions of mobile phone users. Many network vendors, mobile operators, and mobile services providers are enthusiastic about mobile payment, believing mobile payment is to be one of the hot topics in today' service market, creating new meaning for mobile phones.

Mobile Commerce refers to wireless electronic commerce used for conducting commerce or business through a handy device like cellular phone or tablets. It is also said that it is the next generation wireless ecommerce that needs no wire and plug-in devices. Mobile commerce is usually called as 'm-Commerce' in which user can do any sort of transaction including buying and selling of the goods, asking any services, transferring the ownership or rights, transacting and transferring the money by accessing wireless internet service on the mobile handset itself. The next generation of e-commerce would most probably be mobile commerce or m-commerce. Presuming its wide potential reach all major mobile handset manufacturing companies are making WAP enabled smart phones and providing the maximum wireless internet and web

facilities covering personal, official and commerce requirement to pave the way of m-commerce that would later be very fruitful for them.

M-commerce has several major advantages over its fixed counterparts because of its specific inbuilt characteristics such as personalization, flexibility, and distribution. Mobile commerce promises exceptional business, market potential and greater efficiency.

M-commerce can be a huge success for the Indian market but this requires a complete ecosystem, partners must be synchronized so that the best benefits go to consumers and their confidence is assured. Although m-commerce market in India is in nascent stage, m-payment

and m-banking segments have Scorching summer seems to be heating up things on the m-commerce front, for more than half the shopping population has expressed their intent to buy products from their mobiles from the comfort of their homes this season rather than venture out in the sun to a mall. About 59 per cent of shoppers this summer have declared that they would consider shopping on their mobile phones to avoid heat and crowded market areas. Among the hot products this season for mobile shoppers are sunglasses, cotton apparel, tees, shorts and caps and among the favourite colours being white, blue, green, black and cream.

1.1 Objectives: The objective of this research is to study the various modes of mobile payment and find out the current market situation of mobile payment services, also find out the future trend of mobile payment service.

2. Literature Review

Currently, a number of mobile payment procedures, which is a typical application of ICTS, have been used widely from developed countries to developing countries. Mobile payment is an exciting domain, which will rapidly evolve in the years to come (Karnouskos S. & Vilmos A., 2004). Today, mobile payments mainly pay for popular mobile content and services since there 79 Junying Zhong are few alternative payment solutions available. Other successful applications include ticketing and vending (Mallat N., et al., 2004). However, these are still niche, not mainstream applications.

Mobile payment, also known as m-payment, is a new and alternative payment method wherein a mobile device is involved in the payment process in order to initiate, authorize and/or confirm an exchange of financial value in return for a wide range of services and digital or hard goods, instead of paying with cash, check or credit cards (Karnouskos S. & Vilmos A., 2004; Au Y.A. & Kauffman R. J., 2008; Dahlberg T., et al., 2007; Karnouskos S. & Fokus F., 2004). This definition includes a wide palette of approaches, and points out the fact that mobile payments do not restrict themselves to payments via mobile phone but can be made with virtually any mobile device such as smart-phone, PDA, tablet PC or even merchant-operated terminals (Karnouskos S. & Vilmos A., 2004).

The high growth rate of mobile handset diffusion in the 1990s is one of the tremendous success stories of the telecommunications industry, but it has slowed in recent years. Despite

a widely reported economic slowdown in 2008, the global mobile handset market has been unaffected by the present economic slowdown. If there was one highlight in 2008, it was that the smart-phone segment grew 22.5 percent, according to IDC's Worldwide Mobile Phone Tracker report (IDC, 2009). Mobile payment transaction values for digital and physical goods to exceed \$300bn globally within five years, and forecasts total mobile payments to grow nearly tenfold by 2013, according to Juniper Research (Juniper Research, 2008).

In order to complete an m-commerce transaction, a customer needs to exchange values, goods and services with a wireless mobile device. This monetary transaction that is associated with m-commerce is called a mobile payment. A mobile payment (m-payment) is defined as “a payment where a mobile device is used to initiate, authorize and confirm an exchange of financial value in return for goods and services” (Abu Bakar & S. Osman 2005)

Mobile commerce (m-commerce) refers to exchanging products and services via mobile telecommunications networks. M-commerce has many applications, such as mobile shopping, mobile marketing, mobile banking, mobile ticketing, mobile entertainment and others. (P., Tarasewich, R.C., Nickerson, and M., Warkentin 2001)

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Research Type

The research is of qualitative in nature

3.2. Data Collection

Secondary data is used for this study. The data will be obtained from different research papers, and Internet and mobile association of India (IAMAI).

4. An Analysis of M-commerce services In India.

4.1 M-commerce and mPayment services in India

Bill Payments – With the mPayment services, paying all types of utility bills such as water, electricity and gas bills has become much more convenient via mobile phone. People can pay their bill from anywhere and anytime via their mobile phone, thereby they do not need to stand in a queue therefore they can save their lots of time.

xpWallet announced its launch of mWallet Bill Pay offering, enabling users to receive and view bills instantly through the Internet, USSD and SMS.

Money Transfer – Funds transfer is one of the unique features of mobile commerce services. Previously, people would require going online on a computer to transfer the funds between one to another bank account. Now, one can easily send money to anyone, anywhere; or transfer money between bank accounts through mobile devices within a few seconds.

Retail Transactions – With the rise in shopping malls and retail stores in India, mCommerce & mPayments services are extremely valuable for customers for making payments at the checkouts. Additionally, these services also make online shopping much easier and lucrative for both the customers and merchants through various discounts and loyalty coupons.

Movie Ticketing – Mobile commerce services also enable users to book movie tickets via a mobile phone. Now, people can enjoy watching movies by planning for that anytime in an easier and hassle free manner.

Travel Ticketing – Now, scheduling any trip to anywhere and anytime has become convenient with the mCommerce services available in India. People are now able to book train or flight tickets via their mobile phone and have the pleasure of the journey.

Mobile commerce adoption has increased significantly in the country due to multiple factors such as enhanced 3G penetration and availability of affordable smartphones. India is expected to have close to 503 million mobile Internet users by March 2017, The overall internet user base (wireline and wireless) in the country stood at approximately 350 million as on June 2015 and is estimated to touch 503 million by 2017, the report titled 'India on the go-mobile Internet Vision' by IMAI and KPMG said. "The number of mobile internet users in India was approximately 159 million in 2014. This number is expected to continue to grow rapidly and reach 314 million by end of year 2017 registering a CAGR of 27.8% for the period 2013-2017," the report said

It further said, 2G user base in the country is projected to decline in the coming years as more and more customers are expected to migrate to 3G.

The report said that 3G user base in India is rapidly gaining market and is projected to grow at a CAGR of 61.3% between 2013-17. Up from 87.1 million in December 2012 as more people are accessing the web through mobile devices and tablets. It is being said that, in the next three years mobile commerce will constitute more than 25 percent of the total traffic in e-retailing. Mobile Commerce market in India to grow at pace of 71.06 percent over the period 2012-2016.

According to Analysys Mason's research (published in our recent report more than USD20 billion was transferred over m-payment services in eight countries in EMAP in 2012, and this is set to grow significantly in the next 5 years to more than USD90 billion.

Analysis Mason identified 61 m-payment deployments in 17 countries in EMAP, and China and India accounted for more than a third of them. Operators are not the only ones providing m-payment services – only 29% of surveyed services are solely run by operators

The forecast shows the number of smart phone user in India from 2013 to 2019. For 2016, the number of smartphone user in India is estimated to reach 204.1 million. India second largest country in the world projected to pass the united states in the numbers of smartphone user in 2017.

Years	Smartphone user in Million in India (Millions)
2013	76
2014	123.3
2015	167.9
2016	204.1
2017	243.8
2018	279.2
2019	317.1

Source:- Statistica 2016

The new concept has already gained much popularity in the **US, Europe, and Africa**. In India, though, basic banking transactions and mobile payments are available, but with the increasing use of Smartphone, tablets, latest-applications enabled mobile devices and increasing 3G penetrations in Indian digital market, the mCommerce service is creating its space in the market that can comply with country regulatory guidelines. However, there are future challenges that the industry needs to face.

Following the path of major player **Kenya’s M-PESA** which has facilitated people mobile banking using mobile devices, in India, RBI and TRAI, financial institutions, operators and service providers have partnered with each other to take mCommerce to rural India. For example, SBI and ICICI bank have partnered with a mobile banking technology partner “EKO” for their mobile banking solutions. Likewise, other banks are also following them.

According to a report by Boston Consulting Group, there is an ample scope for mCommerce in India. At present, India has over 800 million mobile subscribers, including 240 million with bank accounts, and 20 million with credit cards; there are 88,000 bank branches and

70,000 cash points. The additional fact is that the half of Indian households is still unbanked, including 42% holding at least one mobile phone. This opens a great opportunity for mobile phone industry and financial institutions to galvanize mobile commerce services in India.

It is evident that mCommerce and mPayments services have significantly been building its market in India; and in the near future it will grow rapidly. There are some obstacles such as security of financial transactions and speed of user interfaces. Another major obstacle to m-commerce in India is meeting the **Know Your Customers (KYC)** norms. Though, following Kenya's **National ID system** which propelled its m-commerce to a huge success, if India gets its **Unique Identity Development Authority of India (UIDAI) or Aadhar** project successfully implemented, mobile commerce will rise in India to become the next generation mCommerce for its mass adoption.

5. Conclusion

Mobile commerce is going to play a major role in mpayment conducting business in future. Future of m-commerce services is very difficult to predict. With heated competition in markets, different mpayment strategies, and more customer awareness give a boost to mobile commerce services growth. That will be change the mpayment pattern. There are some important factors that will significantly contribute the boom of M-commerce industries in India. Retailer takes the advantage of various mpayment and in the same time they can make the electronic order and should be in touch with customers all the time. People are getting in touched with m-commerce. They can make the electronic order anytime and anywhere.

Mobile commerce services will certainly be successful in India, but telecom companies and banks do need to spend more to provide safety and security from intrusions and hacking. Further, they also need to build awareness among the consumers by embracing the technology and promoting it ingenuously.

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